

MESOPP

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micronekton modelling**

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1. Overview

MESOPP (Mesopelagic Southern Ocean Prey and Predators) is a European H2020 International Cooperation project to enhancing and focusing research and innovation cooperation with Australia. The underlying concept of MESOPP is the creation of a collaborative network and associated e-infrastructure (marine ecosystem information system) between European and Australian research teams/institutes sharing similar interests in the Southern Ocean and Antarctica, its marine ecosystem functioning and the rapid changes occurring with the climate warming and the exploitation of marine resources.

In the past 30 years, facing global knowledge issues, lacking data, addressing huge modelling challenges, we observed the successful world organisation of meteorology. These past 15 years, Europe has kick started and demonstrated similar successful structuring of the operational oceanography fostered by the Copernicus initiative (<http://marine.copernicus.eu/>), today worldwide used and recognised, fully anticipated and integrated in GOOS (Global Ocean Observing System), IOSS (Integration ocean observation system), SOOS (Southern Ocean Observing System), GODAE (the international global ocean data assimilation experiment), and IMBER (integrated marine biogeochemistry and ecosystem research).

A major R&D strategic challenge is to connect the marine ecosystem community across the fields of meteorology, climate, oceanography and biology. Lack of data, development of accurate high end models, global coverage and need for exchange are issues that need to be overcome.

While MESOPP will focus on the enhancement of collaborations by eliminating various obstacles in establishing a common methodology and a connected network of databases of acoustic data for the estimation of micronekton biomass and validation of models, it will also contribute to a better predictive understanding of the SO based on furthering the knowledge base on key functional groups of micronekton and processes which determine ecosystem dynamics from physics to large oceanic predators. This first project and associated implementation (science network and specification of an infrastructure) should constitute the nucleus of a larger international programme of acoustic monitoring and micronekton modelling to be integrated in the general framework of ocean observation following a roadmap that will be prepared during the project.

Partners

- CLS, Collecte Localisation Satellites, France
- CSIRO: Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation, Australia
- UTas: University of Tasmania, Australia
- AAD: Australian Antarctic Division, Australia
- BAS: Natural environment Research Council NERC-BAS United Kingdom
- UPMC : Université Pierre et Marie Curie France
- IMR: Institute of Marine Research (Havforskninginstituttet) Norway
- UA: University of St Andrew, United Kingdom

2. Agenda and participants

Saturday 10th September

Ecosystem modelling session (conveners: Andrew Constable and Patrick Lehodey)

- 09:00 Introduction
- 11:00 Presentations of current status
- 14:00 Discussion of current project and deliveries
- 16:00 Planning for the MESOPP project

Outline the models to be considered the data inputs - outputs spatial and temporal scales

What is currently possible - advantages and disadvantages of various approaches. Key regional areas

Monday 11th September

Acoustic data session (conveners: Sophie Fielding and Rudy Kloster)

- 09:00 Introduction
- 11:30 Presentation of current status
- 14:00 Discussion of project deliveries
- 16:00 Planning for project deliveries

Outline acoustic data - processing availability etc, other data? Known issues - new technologies - spatial and temporal issues - reference sites

Tuesday 12th September

Observation model session (conveners Nils Handegard and Rudy Kloster)

- 09:00 Introduction
- 11:00 Presentation of current status
- 14:00 Discussion of project deliveries
- 16:00 Planning for project deliveries

Outline observation models - model data integration; Acoustic data utilization - development testing

The workshop was organized by the CSIRO and took place on Sat 10 - Tue 13 September at the CSIRO Marine Laboratories, Castray Esp. Hobart, Tasmania. The full list of participants can be found at Attachment A.

3. Introduction

EU Countries and Australia share a long historical interest for the Southern Ocean and Antarctica. After the heroic history of exploration of the southern Ocean and Antarctica, both EU countries and Australia have deployed a substantial effort for monitoring the Southern Ocean. These monitoring programmes include research cruises, animal tracking and acoustic sampling. There are some biological resources already exploited (e.g., krill, Patagonian toothfish, ice fish, lobsters), and the likely huge but poorly estimated biomass of mesopelagic fishes could be a future additional resource of the blue economy.

Conservation and management of exploited marine species in the SO is the responsibility of several international organisations, e.g., the CCAMLR (Commission for the Conservation of Antarctic Marine Living Resources) or the IWC (International Whaling Commission), that have the objectives of maintaining high biodiversity, e.g. in establishing marine protected areas, and to manage fisheries for a sustainable exploitation of fish/krill stocks. This requires a good knowledge of the habitats and behavior of species of interest, and consequently of the dynamics, abundance and distributions of their prey, i.e., the micronekton for most of them. However, data and knowledge on these organisms are missing to develop assessment of these stocks and propose sustainable rules of exploitation. In addition they provide useful ecosystem and climate service by transferring the organic carbon generated from anthropogenic CO₂ through the food chain and daily vertical migrations.

MESOPP proposes to create a collaborative network and associated e-infrastructure between European and Australian research teams/institutes to establish standard methods and datasets to understand, model and estimate the biomass and dynamics of mesopelagic organisms in the Southern Ocean. MESOPP objectives and project partners' activities make this project in synergy with several other EU, Australian or international projects. This includes EU H2020 ATLANTOS and COPERNICUS service evolution GREENUP project, the research of French IPEV and CNRS teams working on arctic regions, Australia Antarctic Division, British Antarctic Survey and the University of St Andrews, as well as the exploration project Polar Pods of Jean Louis Etienne and the Antarctic Circumnavigation Expedition.

With the classical scientific echo-sounder installed onboard research vessels, there is now a large possibility to collect acoustic data from various platforms: vessels, moorings, bottom stations, gliders (Handegard et al 2010). The Australian IMOS programme is a nice initiative that already includes several platforms of acoustic monitoring (Kloser/ web site). While observation systems and monitoring programs are developing, the treatment of the acoustic signal remains a challenging issue. In particular, the acoustic signal is not simply proportional to the density of organisms; there are different sources of variability that need to be accounted before converting signal intensity in biomass density. It is therefore still useful to carry out net sampling during research cruises to characterize ecological provinces and their species associations to provide more accurate conversion.

MESOPP is organized around three themes: acoustic data, models and use cases. The project will provide three references datasets of 38 kHz acoustic data in three different regions of the Southern Ocean (South Indian; South Pacific and South Atlantic). A common methodology and processing of data should be proposed for facilitating the use of these data in the modeling. In particular they will be used to evaluate and validate different modeling approaches (SEAPODYM, ATLANTIS, SIZE-BASED) and help to provide estimation of biomass and potential changes associated to climate change projections. Model outputs and acoustic databases will be made available for inter-comparison and further analyses of behavior and distribution of large marine species. This first workshop of the project is devoted to the standardisation of acoustic data for micronekton modelling and is organized with three thematic sessions to present and discuss the models, the acoustic data and the approach to link both.

4. Ecosystem model and micronekton

Three models were presented during the workshop: Atlantis, a Size Based Model and Seapodym

4.1. Atlantis Model

Beth Fulton presented Atlantis (<http://atlantis.cmar.csiro.au/>). At the core of Atlantis is a deterministic biophysical sub-model, coarsely spatially-resolved in three dimensions, which tracks nutrient (usually N and S) flows through the main biological groups in the system. The primary ecological processes modelled are consumption, production, waste production, migration, predation, recruitment, habitat dependency, and mortality. The trophic resolution is typically at the functional group level. Invertebrates are usually represented as biomass pools (in mg N m^{-3}), while vertebrates are represented using an explicit age-structured formulation (where the size and numbers at age are tracked).

The physical environment is also represented explicitly, via a set of polygons matched to the major geographical and bioregional features of the simulated marine system. The ocean physics is derived from an ocean circulation ROMS model. Biological model components are replicated in each depth layer of each of these polygons. Movement between the polygons is by advective transfer or by directed movements depending on the variable in question.

A configuration of Atlantis is being developed for multiple regions, nesting around the SO-Antarctica region along the Kerguelen-Axis (Figure 1). The model extends from the surface to the seabed, particularly in shelf waters. There are 10 depth layers (0-20 m, 20-50 m, 50-100 m, 100-200 m, 300-400 m, 400-750 m, 750-1000 m, 1000-2000 m, > 2000 m depth).

Figure 1 - Domain of the Atlantis models in the SO-Antarctica region along the Kerguelen-Axis - the smaller model in yellow (24 polygons) will be completed first.

Biologically the model contains 43 biological groups spanning from microscopic primary producers to large whales (Table 1). This structure being used includes two types of mesopelagics: migrant and non-migrant. The acoustic data could be used to evaluate predicted biomass of the mesopelagic groups and potentially other micronekton groups (amongst the zooplankton and finfish).

The structure of Atlantis means that a conversion model will be needed to map from model biomasses (reported both overall across the model domain, but also per depth layer per box) to acoustic data. This means the exact form of the acoustic data used can be flexible and identified in

close consultation with those in charge of the acoustic data sources; noting that 3D rather than 2D data is preferred so as to allow for cross checks against the depth profiles generated by Atlantis.

Table 1: List of species and functional groups in the Atlantis model

Group	Group Type
Ice Diatoms	Biomass pool
Ice Mixotrophs	Biomass pool
Coccolithophores	Biomass pool
Pelagic Picophytoplankton	Biomass pool
Pelagic Diatoms	Biomass pool
Pelagic Dinoflagellates	Biomass pool
Ice Zoobiota	Biomass pool
Microzooplankton	Biomass pool
Mesozooplankton	Biomass pool
Macrozooplankton	Biomass pool
Salps	Biomass pool
Benthic Deposit feeders	Biomass pool
Macrobenthos	Biomass pool
Benthic Filter feeders	Biomass pool
Krill	Age/size structured
Fish Pelagic	Age structured
Fish Mesopelagic	Age structured
Toothfish	Age structured
Icefish	Age structured
Cephalopods	Age structured
Antarctic Fur Seal	Age structured
Elephant Seal	Age structured
Crabeater Seal	Age structured
Leopard Seal	Age structured
Other Seal	Age structured
Adelie Penguin	Age structured
Emperor Penguin	Age structured
Other Penguins	Age structured
Albatross	Age structured
Skuas	Age structured
Other Seabirds	Age structured
Minke Whales	Age structured
Other Baleen Whales	Age structured
Orca A	Age structured
Orca B	Age structured
Orca C	Age structured
Sperm Whales	Age structured
Pelagic Bacteria	Biomass pool
Sediment bacteria	Biomass pool
Ice Bacteria	Biomass pool
Labile Detritus	Biomass pool
Refractory Detritus	Biomass pool
Carrion	Biomass pool

4.2. Size Based Model

Julia Blanchard and Rowan Trebilco presented a general introduction to the dynamical size spectra models, which focus on body size rather than species (Blanchard et al. 2011, Scott et al. 2014). Size spectrum ecological models are representations of a community of individuals which grow and change trophic levels. A key emergent feature of such a representation by size and trophic levels is a decreasing trend in abundance, i.e., the size spectrum (Figure 2). Dynamic size spectrum models can be implemented from the R package ‘mizer’ (Scott et al 2014) either under the form of community model, where individuals are only characterized by their size; the trait-based model, where individuals are further characterized by their asymptotic size; and the multispecies model where additional trait differences are resolved. One example of implementation (Blanchard et al. 2011) incorporates dynamic interactions between marine benthic (detritus-based) and pelagic (primary producer based) pathways to investigate how the coupling of these pathways affects food web stability and resilience (Figure 2). The model has been also applied to a global scale in 2D representation (Figure 3).

One key objective with MESOPP will be to investigate how to evaluate the size based model from acoustic data, or how to “observe” acoustics from size spectrum models? Empirical studies are needed to characterize body size functional groups with their average acoustic target strengths. Then, the regional distributions and spatial patchiness of these groups can be identified from survey design and ships of opportunity sampling using environmental variables (e.g., temperature). The model will have to be parameterized. Ideally, an observation model outputs should be fitted to acoustic data to estimate parameters and uncertainty (see section 6).

Figure 2 - Conceptual representation of the size-based modelling approach (Blanchard et al. 2009, 2011, 2012)

Figure 3 - Predicted average distribution of biomass of oceanic pelagic predators above 10 cm in size according to the size-based modeling approach (Blanchard et al. ?)

Rowan Trebilco is developing an implementation of this modelling approach to the Kerguelen axis area using the ‘*mizer*’ R package. While ‘*mizer*’ has traditionally only been used for modelling fish, with lower and higher trophic levels being represented as boundary conditions or mortality terms respectively, zooplankton and higher predator will be modelled explicitly for the Kerguelen axis area. ‘*mizer*’ is not spatially explicit, hence species distributions and water column use are to be represented using an availability matrix to constrain possible predator-prey interactions based on relative overlap of habitat.

The model outputs will be evaluated against data collected during the last Australian research cruise in the Kerguelen axis (the K-axis voyage). On this voyage the mesopelagic community was sampled using an IYGPT (International Young Gadoid Pelagic Trawl) net equipped with a MIDOC (MIDwater Opening/Closing) multiple cod-end device that allowed the catch to be split into five 200m strata to 1000m (Figure 4). Some 17,000 individual fishes had been photographed, identified and measured when processing catch at sea. This sampling provides a key source of information for model development and evaluation.

Figure 4: the mesopelagic net equipped with MIDOC system onboard the Australian research Vessel (left) and the track of the research cruise superimposed on chlorophyll estimate from ocean color satellite data.

The following discussion concerned the definition of the groups of species and the need to characterize the vertical behaviour and the type of response to the acoustic signal. For intercomparison purpose the model will fit in the same polygons of Atlantis Model. Currently, six groups are envisaged:

Small myctophids

- *Electrona antarctica*
- *Electrona carlsbergi*
- *Kreffichthys anderssoni*
- *Protomyctophum spp.*
- *Metaelectrona ventralis*
- *Diap^hus hudsoni*

Large myctophids

- *Gymnoscopelus spp.*
- *Lampanyctus spp.*
- *Nannobranchium spp.*

Gonostomatiids

- *Cyclothone microdon*
- *Cyclothone pseudopallida*

Other mesopelagics

- *Notolepis coatsi*
- *Paradiplospinus gracilis*
- *Melanonus spp.*

Bathypelagics

- *Bathylagus spp.*
- *Cynomacurus spp.*
- *Benthabella spp.*

Squids

- *Onychoteuthiids*
- *Ommastrephiids*
- *Small-medium nektonic squids*

4.3. SEAPODYM Model

Anna Conchon and Patrick Lehodey presented the SEAPODYM model and the data assimilation framework to use acoustic data for optimal parameterisation.

SEAPODYM is an Eulerian modeling framework including several functional groups at low and mid-trophic levels and detailed population dynamics for target species, e.g. tunas. The Mid-Trophic Level (MTL) module simulates spatial and temporal dynamics of production and biomass of six functional groups of micronekton (Lehodey et al. 1998, 2010, 2015) for the oceanic epi- and mesopelagic layers (0-1000m), with a system of advection-diffusion-reaction equations (Figure 5). The same modeling approach can be applied to simulate one additional group of mesozooplankton that is also a key component of the marine ecosystem.

Figure 5: Identification of MTL functional groups on acoustic echogram (a) and conceptual model (b) (from Lehodey et al. (2015)).

Top: 1.1: Epipelagic; 2.1: migrant upper mesopelagic; 2.2: upper mesopelagic; 3.1: highly migrant lower mesopelagic; 3.2: migrant lower mesopelagic; 3.3: lower. **Bottom:** Example of an acoustic transect showing bio-acoustic layers and the depth limits between them.

A preliminary parameterization of energy transfer from the primary production to the functional groups of micronekton was achieved based on a first compilation of existing data in the literature and a Pacific basin-scale simulation (Lehodey et al., 2010). But a robust statistical approach to optimize the parameters based on the Maximum likelihood Estimation has been implemented to estimate these parameters directly from observation, especially acoustic data (Lehodey et al 2015). Six parameters in the model have to be estimated. The first one (E) defines the total energy transfer between primary production and all the MTL groups. The other parameters are the relative coefficients (E'_n), redistributing this energy through the different components (the sum of which being 1). The parameterization of E requires absolute biomass estimates of MTL, while the matrix of E'_n coefficients can be estimated simply using relative day and night values integrated in the three vertical layers of the model.

The model is quite sensitive to the oceanic currents and it has been shown that despite ocean data assimilation, reanalyses by ocean circulation models are not always matching the real mesoscale activity. Large marine animal tracking data with electronic tags provide an interesting indirect

observation of the quality of physical mesoscale prediction since they are clearly associated with mesoscale structure (eddies, fronts) that concentrate their prey (micronekton). The exceptional animal tracking datasets of elephant seals, fur seals, penguins, and seabirds collected in the SO are ideal for indirect validation (Figure 6).

Figure 6 - Predicted micronekton fields and observed elephant seal movement

Top: SEAPODYM-MTL outputs of epipelagic (left) and lower mesopelagic (right) functional groups of micronekton around Kerguelen Islands. Bottom: Mesoscale distribution of MTL biomass in the southern ocean (east of Kerguelen Is.) predicted from (left) the $1/12^\circ$ CMEMS High resolution ocean circulation model outputs and (right) the $1/4^\circ$ CMEMS GLO-OBS (based on satellite altimetry). The GPS track of the same elephant seal (superimposed white or black line) suggests a better positioning of eddies from GLO-OBS, coherent with the foraging behavior of the seal.

Several SEAPODYM-MTL simulations should be produced and made available together with their forcing variables to the project partners. The MTL model is driven by physical (temperature and currents) and biogeochemical data (net primary production, euphotic depth) on the same domain and at the same time/spatial resolution. The input forcing dataset consists in:

- Temperature: in degrees Celsius
- Currents, zonal and vertical: in m/s
- Vertically integrated Net primary production: in $\text{mmolC}/\text{m}^2/\text{d}$
- Euphotic depth (m)

A reference simulation ($1/4^\circ \times$ week) is used as a starting point and to test model improvements. It is based on CMEMS / Mercator-Ocean physical variables (GLORYS2v4 and PSY3R3v3). With the same biogeochemical fields (satellite derived PP and Zeu), one additional simulation based on the CMEMS GLO-OBS product providing currents directly derived from satellite altimetry data could be useful for comparison.

During the discussion, it was proposed to evaluate the sensitivity of the model outputs to the definition of the vertical layer boundaries currently based on the euphotic depth, and also to different processing methods of a same acoustic data set. Co-located oceanographic and acoustic data should help to verify the suitability of the vertical layer boundary definition in the arctic waters. It seems also necessary to test different forcing variables, especially currents and primary production fields. Finally the parameterization in the special case of shallow waters with depths allowing only one or two vertical layers could be revised if there is available information.

4.4. Modeling session Discussion

The intercomparison between the three modelling approaches is acknowledged as a real strength of the project. To facilitate the evaluation with acoustic observation, the models should share at least one similar regional domain and units as far as possible and provide clear methodology for comparison when they differ in their outputs, e.g. aggregation of several functional groups from one model to be compared to one single group from another model. Each model will at least cover the Indian SO between Antarctica and the North of Kerguelen plateau.

A report providing documentation of the models, the approaches for standardization and protocols to be used for model inter-comparisons is expected as a deliverable of the project (t0+12). This should help to establish the catalogue and data access service needed to design the central information service (CIS).

In addition to acoustic and model data, there are large datasets of micronekton predators (elephant seals, seals, penguins, sea birds) that represent great opportunity to test the model outputs and compare different regions of the SO. Interestingly, the European project EO4wildlife (<http://eo4wildlife.eu/>) will develop an open service platform with an intuitive interoperable toolbox “allowing accessing dedicated big data services for processing geospatial environmental simulations”. It would be useful and a great achievement to establish a link between these different databases and e-infrastructure.

A series of metrics should be developed and shared between partners to evaluate the model simulation outputs. Examples of metrics are:

- The Pearson correlation (R) measures how well the model predicts the variability of observations;
- The normalized variance (Var) measures how well the model represents the amplitude in the variability of observations (the closest to 1, the better);
- The centered root-mean-squared-error (RMSE) measures how big are the errors between observation and data (after calibration of α coefficients);
- the R-squared goodness of fit (RSGF) measures how well the model fits the data, namely whether the model is a better descriptor of the data than the mean of the data itself.

These metrics are given by the following formulae:

$$R = \frac{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (B_{i,mod} - \bar{B}_{mod})(B_{i,obs} - \bar{B}_{obs})}{\sigma_{mod} \sigma_{obs}}$$

$$Var = \left(\frac{\sigma_{mod}}{\sigma_{obs}} \right)^2$$

$$RMSE = \sigma_{mod} + \sigma_{obs} - 2\sigma_{mod}\sigma_{ref}R$$

$$RSGF = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (B_{i,mod} - B_{i,obs})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (B_{i,obs} - \bar{B}_{obs})^2}$$

Models outputs and observations (physical oceanography, biogeochemical and biological data) should help to characterize large bio-geographic provinces and their variability. Then the impact of climate change in these SO bio-geographic provinces should be investigated using model simulations with physical forcings from IPCC-type Earth Climate models. A series of projection are/will be available through the CMIP5 and CMIP6 (Eyring et al 2016) projects. Based on past experiences in using IPCC Earth Climate model outputs, a special attention should be given to the potential biases existing in these models. Earth Climate models are starting to be implemented with higher resolution ($1/4^\circ$) than in the past. Australia has several simulations already that cover the SO, and include also biogeochemical coupling.

4.5. ACTIONS AND DELIVERABLES:

- List of deliverables

N°	Title	Due date	Resp.
D4.1	Documentation of the models, approaches for standardization and protocols to be used for model inter-comparison	31/05/2017	UTas
D4.3	Methods to rapidly aggregate acoustic data from vessels of opportunity for use in model validation	31/05/2018	UTas
D4.4	Statistical methods for estimating skill of mesopelagic models to replicate acoustic observations	30/11/2018	CLS
D4.5	Report on model-intercomparison	31/05/2019	UTas

- List of actions

Issue	Proposition
List of state variables, units and format for each model (Atlantis, SEAPODYM-MTL, and Size-Based)	Develop a matrix of association between functional/species groups groups of the models
Table of conversion factors between units	g C <-> wet weight by group of species?
Check common domain and time period between models and covered by observations	Define temporal and space coverage of datasets
Request same acoustic data set processed with different methodology/software for model sensitivity analysis	Anna visiting BAS to work on MD II acoustic data using the echoview software

5. Acoustic data

Three reference datasets will be prepared from existing and new acquired data. Available databases were presented.

5.1. IMOS Project

Rudy Kloser presented AODN portal (<https://portal.aodn.org.au/>) and the datasets associated to the IMOS project (<http://imos.org.au/>). Bio-acoustic observations with echosounders at single and multiple frequencies have been acquired, processed and publicly available between 2010 and 2016 from 17 vessels covering 300,000 km (Figure 7). They have been deployed on research, large fishing and geophysical survey vessels to estimate mid-trophic level organism distribution and abundance focused around the Tasman Sea, Southern Pacific Ocean, southern Indian Ocean and the Australian Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) deep oceanic environments (Figure 7). The primary data-type recorded from the vessel-mounted echosounder systems is georeferenced calibrated water column volume backscatter, Sv [dB re 1 m⁻¹].

Figure 7 - Acoustic data (black line) acquired, processed and publicly available between 2010 and 2016 from 17 vessels covering 300,000 km for the IMOS bio-acoustic program.

A number of vessels are participating in the bio-acoustics program depending on location and availability. Most of the vessels are commercial fishing vessels that have agreed to record data during transits to and from fishing grounds, while others are scientific research vessels collecting underway acoustic data during transits and science operations. All vessels collect 38 kHz but increasingly 18 kHz acoustic data from either Simrad EK60, ES60 or ES70 echosounders. In all cases the 38 kHz echosounders are connected to Simrad ES38B transducers. The RV Aurora Australis and the now ceased RV Southern Surveyor collect concurrent acoustic data at frequencies including 12, 38, 120 and 200 kHz. The new CSIRO Marine National Facility vessel RV Investigator is the latest vessel to join the program and collects data with Simrad EK60 split beam echosounders at 18, 38, 70, 120, 200 and 333 kHz.

Bio-acoustic data are delivered in a delayed mode under the form of calibrated acoustic volume backscatter at 38 kHz (as well as 12, 18, 70, 120 and 200 kHz where available) at a spatial resolution of 10 m depth by 1 km long, down to a nominal depth of 1000 m designed to capture mesoscale - 10's km processes. Processing of the data is described in Ryan et al. (2015). The visualization tool is written in Matlab (but a python version exists).

The outputs (Figure 8) are in netcdf files (CF standard) and they contain at least unfiltered data (raw data integrated over 1 km and 10 depth resolution) and filtered data (at the same resolution). Quality control and indicators (number of ping discarded during the processing, noise information) are also included (Ryan et al 2015). Horizontal resolution of 1 km is coarse when compared to fish school detection and processing at 100 m resolution is applied when this is an objective of the

analysis /study. If there is a broad science need, all IMOS bioacoustics data could be provided at 100 m resolution.

The processing uses depth and temperature (currently CARS climatology) to correct for sound absorption and depth. Sensitivity of the data to the environment can be explored by the user when other oceanographic data is available.

Figure 8 - Example of the fishing vessel acoustic data from Australia to New Zealand.

Acoustic data at 38 kHz over three years in the austral winter highlighting the localised (10's km) and geographic (100's km) spatial scales and the localised (less than 12 hrs), diel (greater than 24 hrs), and yearly temporal scales recorded in the data (Kloser et al., 2009).

5.2. SONA

Sophie Fielding presented the Southern Ocean Network of Acoustics (<https://sona.aq/>) initiative. SONA represents a group of partners (Australia, France, New Zealand, Norway, the UK and USA) who have united to measure the mid-trophic level of the ecosystem; to agree on common standards and protocols for data collection and processing, and with a view to provide that data on an open access basis. SONA database is under construction and is not yet available. A recent workshop was held in Vigo in April 2016 with the participation of US colleagues: Charles Anderson from the National Centers for Environmental Information (NCEI), USA) and John Horne (University of Washington, USA). The workshop discussed the issues for standardisation of acoustic data from both research and fisheries vessels into a common accessible database. These objectives are obviously shared by MESOPP and both projects should benefit of this synergy. The summary of the workshop discussion is of great help for starting the work of MESOPP:

Data availability

Active acoustic produces large volumes of data and a number of initiatives now exist to appropriately extract and document metadata, and facilitate the distribution, e.g., International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES 2013); the IMOS-BASOOP (above), the NCEI (<https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/>) in USA, and SONA (in development, <https://sona.aq/>).

NCEI: Consists of 26.19TB of archived acoustic data (10.8TB of EK60 data), of which 13.8 TB has been delivered to users. Data is collected from 23 vessels, with most measurements made in US coastal waters. Raw metadata are stored according to ICES 19115-2 metadata standards

SONA-SASD (South Atlantic Science Database): As of June 2016, this data set comprised of 49 surveys (approx. 190,000 km) of raw metadata from British Antarctic Survey (BAS, UK; 1.23 TB), raw file metadata from the Institute for Marine Research (IMR, Norway; 6 surveys) and US Antarctic Marine Living resources (AMLR, USA; 7 surveys) of the Scotia Sea, Antarctica. Raw metadata are stored according to ICES metadata schema.

Data processing techniques

A first comparative analysis of acoustic processing techniques with the same transect indicates some variability in the product output, despite all parties undertaking the same process as written on paper (ASAM 2016).

During the SONA workshop, a similar exercise using the same transects and software (Echoview™) concerned:

- the *Tangaroa* transect, processed by BAS, CSIRO and NIWA. Outputs (mean volume backscattering strength S_v , in dB re 1m^{-1}) were similar (Figure 8) though not totally identical. Differences possibly due to variability in filters applied; and selection of the first data point binned within Echoview™.
- the JCR and the Janas transects, processed by BAS and CSIRO. Estimates of S_v were also very much similar but with BAS generated values lower than the CSIRO estimates. It was noted that all three methods used the same routines and similar filters to remove noise (see Ryan et al. 2015), but they were executed differently, i.e. not in the same sequential order.

There was a consensus for the creation of reference datasets that could be used to test new processing algorithms, and how they would influence processed data output. The NCEI offered to host these datasets.

Figure 9 : Water column mean volume backscattering S_v (dB re 1m^{-1}) along-track from the RV *Tangaroa* transect as processed by BAS (blue), CSIRO (red) and NIWA (green). From Fielding et al. (2016).

Metrics of data quality

CSIRO method for processing data provides a number of metrics that are potentially an indicator of data quality (Signal-to-noise versus range, quantity (and location) of data rejected as a result of processing, background noise estimate), however it was noted that the reasons why the numbers change does not always depend on data quality (for example, data can be rejected because it is below the seabed). One area of focus was whether the signal to noise ratio could be used to identify the usable range of acoustic data. CSIRO noted that they collected data at 38 kHz using a 2

ms pulse length in order to achieve a minimum range of 1000 m of data when using a range of vessels with different noise characteristics.

5.3. French acoustic data (IPEV/TAAF)

Anna Conchon presented bio-acoustic data available from the French programmes using the R.V. Marion Dufresne II in the SO. The vessel is a multi-function ship and has two main missions for oceanographic research, under IPEV's responsibility and logistical support for the French subantarctic islands: Crozet, Kerguelen, Amsterdam/Saint-Paul, under the TAAF's responsibility.

Between 2013 and 2015, acoustic data with a SIMRAD EK60 echo-sounder were collected during the French ANR Mycto3Dmap project (P.I.: Yves Chérel). The Ship was refitted in 2015 with a new multi-beam echosounder EK80. Since 2016 and the end of Mycto3Dmap the new project THEMISTO (Toward Hydroacoustics and Ecology of Mid-trophic levels in Indian and Southern Ocean) is in charge of acoustic data collection (PI: Cédric Cotté) onboard Marion Dufresne. The objective is to study the 3-D distribution of zooplankton and micronekton and their variability related to physical processes and climate. The project will use the new acoustic devices that equip the Marion Dufresne II to acquire 5 frequencies (18-38-70-120-200 kHz) associated with ADCP (3 frequencies 38-75-150 kHz) during transits between La Reunion-Crozet-Kerguelen-Amsterdam-La Reunion to *i*) distinguish groups and species of zooplankton and micronekton and *ii*) characterize the variability of their 3-D distribution along an important latitudinal gradient (from tropical to polar areas).

Physical processes will be investigated simultaneously (*in-situ* data from the thermosalinograph and remotely-sensed analysis) to define multi-scale critical habitats of keystone species in ecosystems of southern Indian Ocean. Along the transects there are regular oceanographic stations with the OISO (Ocean Indien Service d'Observations) program that provide profiles of geo-referenced oceanographic data (<http://campagnes.flotteoceanographique.fr/series/228/fr/index.htm>). The combination of OISO and acoustic measurements provide very useful co-localized measures that can help to characterize and model the mesopelagic ecosystem (Figure 10).

Figure 10 - Example of co-located profiles of acoustic signal (NASC) and physical and biogeochemical variables collected at the same station OISO in 2014 and 2015.

Acoustic data transects for 2013 and 2014 have been processed using IFREMER software (EchOPEN). Data for 2015 et 2016 need to be processed. The EchOPEN is an open source code (Figure 11). It is a Matlab® toolbox for multi-frequency acoustic data processing coupled to MOVIES3D (Trenkel et al. 2009) for visualization. It requires Matlab and Movies3D (64 bits, on Windows 7 and upper versions) and can be obtained at https://svn.mpl.ird.fr/echopen/Echopen_V1.7/ once registered to gildas.roudaut@ird.fr.

Figure 11 - EchOPEN organizational chart (G. Roudaut).

5.4. Acoustic data session discussion

Following the presentations, several issues were discussed and would require interactions between MESOPP partners. A first clarification concerned the position of MESOPP project with the existing initiatives. It was made clear that MESOPP e-infrastructure is not designed to archive acoustic data that are already archived by other projects (note that the storage and access of French acoustic data collected by the M.D II need to be defined). Instead, it should gather the standardized data at the predefined resolution selected by the modelling teams (at least after step C in Figure 11, and even likely some other specific steps based on modelling requirements).

Once an agreement will be achieved on the resolution the three datasets (Indian, Atlantic and Pacific SO) should be prepared and provided under a NetCDF format. These files will be documented and accessible through the MESOPP web site. A new product associate to MESOPP could be the oceanographic data (satellite or model) along the acoustic track; all at the same resolution to facilitate the analyses. The daily $1/12^\circ$ horizontal resolution (~ 9 km) with 10 m vertical resolution seems a good compromise to investigate mesoscale patterns and individual animal tracking as well as basin scale micronekton distributions and characteristics.

The different levels of data processing and outputs can be compared to other types of Earth Observation data acquisition and processing. For instance, satellite data is classically characterized by different product levels from L0 (sensor output) to L4 (gridded interpolated product) to which could correspond similar processing steps for bio-acoustic data (Figure 12). There are also sub-levels (e.g., sublevels should be associated to each filtering step: L2a, L2b...) to better characterize

the different types of products. This parallel seems interesting to follow for the categorization of products and standard format as well as to define their level of accessibility and metadata, including reference to original file and subsequent calibration and quality control processing. For satellite data, typically L0 and L1 are stored and available only on request while L2 to L4 are available online.

Figure 12 - Comparison of processing workflow of satellite and bio-acoustic data

The presentations made clear that the same raw acoustic data can generate outputs with some discrepancies according to the software and even its version. The comparison exercise with ECHOVIEW is particularly useful and should be extended with the EchOPEN software. It was noted that different temperature sources (e.g., climatology or the closest ARGO float profile) were used for correction while the comparison should use the same. Rather than climatology or ARGO profiles that can be sometimes distant from the acoustic profile, it was suggested to use temperature fields from operational ocean circulation models (assimilating surface satellite data and vertical profiles, including those collected with elephant seals in the region). A consensus should be also achieved to standardize the threshold values of high and low pass filter, the filtering of background noise, and the processing of the NaN values.

It will be interesting also to test how the models are sensitive to the discrepancies observed from the different processing steps. Given the much coarse resolution used by models usually, and how the signal is used (e.g., SEAPODYM uses relative signal instead of absolute value), these differences may have no or small impact. This can be verified using the maximum likelihood estimation framework of the SEAPODYM model and a reference dataset processed following the 3 different approaches (IMOS, BAS, and IFREMER).

Another verification should concern the use of new echosounders as the last generation EK-80. Ideally for intercalibration, there would need however the same transect recorded by both type of echo sounders.

Finally, three other acoustic programs/providers that could be interested in participating in the MESOPP project have been identified.

- The US NOAA's National Centers for Environmental Information (NCEI). It provides public access to archived environmental data including bio-acoustic data collected with EK60 echosounder.
- The British Oceanographic Data Center (BODC) archives various meteorological and oceanographic data, including those collected during the regular Atlantic Meridional Transect (AMT) cruises. Active acoustic is recorded during some of these transects and extend to the South Atlantic Ocean. The Atlantic Meridional Transect (AMT) project is a UK NERC funded observing program that collects data from the UK to the Southern Ocean

annually. Active acoustic data are periodically collected during this cruise and could contribute to the MESOPP program.

- The National Institute of Water and Atmospheric Research (NIWA) of New Zealand conducts research cruises including bio-acoustic recording in the Southern Ocean and Antarctica area.

It is proposed to invite their PIs to be involved in the discussion for the roadmap.

5.5. ACTIONS AND DELIVERABLES:

- List of deliverable

N°	Title	Due date	Resp.
D3.1	Acoustic processing routine and quality checking methods	31/05/2018	BAS
D3.2	Reference dataset of 38 KHz acoustic backscatter for SO Atlantic sector	30/11/2017	BAS
D3.3	Reference dataset of 38 KHz acoustic backscatter for SO Indian sector	30/11/2017	UPMC
D3.4	Reference dataset of 38 KHz acoustic backscatter for SO Pacific sector	30/11/2017	CSIRO
D3.5	Collocated NASC and Oceanographic variables	30/11/2017	UPMC

- List of actions

Issue	Proposition
Define a common resolution to which the 3 acoustic data sets will be aggregated and stored	Horizontal 1km x 10m vertical resolution as in IMOS?
Define a common metadata and catalogue	Vinca provides an example
List all transects available by dataset with their metadata	Data covering the period 2010-2017?
Define where acoustic datasets are stored and accessible through MESOPP CIS.	If not accessible these datasets need to be stored on MESOPP web site server.

6. Observation Model

Even if the acoustic signal is roughly proportional to the density of marine organisms, there are various issues to account for converting the signal in biomass. Therefore, there is a need to construct an observation model to compare observations (acoustic signal) and ecosystem model predictions (biomass) taking into account the non-linear relationship between taxa and acoustics and adding noise modeling. The session was kicked off by presentations on how to link models and acoustic observing system.

6.1. 1st observation model tested with SEAPODYM

Anna Conchon presented the approach used with SEAPODYM to estimate model parameters directly from acoustic signal. The parameter estimation approach is based on a cost function that uses relative ratio of acoustic signal during daytime and nighttime in the 3 vertical layers of the model that are compared to similar ratio of predicted biomass. The acoustic signal (S_A) gives the acoustic density by surface area. To convert this value into biomass of organisms (B), i.e. the simple model prediction unit, it has to be weighted by the acoustic strength of organisms inhabiting the water column using the following equation:

$$B = \frac{W \cdot s_A}{4\pi\sigma_{bs}} \quad \text{or} \quad B = \alpha S_A \quad \text{with} \quad \alpha = \frac{W}{4\pi\sigma_{bs}}$$

where W is the mean weight of organisms and σ_{bs} the backscattering cross-section, which depend on the acoustic response of different micronektonic organisms and so may vary between model vertical layers.

The first analyses have been conducted in CLS to simply adjust the α coefficient by layer and transect. These preliminary results give a strong clustering between Indian Ocean and Pacific data for the epipelagic layer but much more homogeneous results for the lower mesopelagic layer (Figure 13). Reasons that can explain these results need to be explored.

It was also shown that the model can be used to develop Observing System Simulation Experiments (OSSE) with the possibility of adding noise in the forcing and pseudo-observations. This kind of analysis can provide key information to test and design a sampling network.

Anna Conchon will embark onboard the French RV Marion Dufresne II in January 2017 to collect acoustic data between La Reunion and the French Austral Islands.

Figure 13 - Ratio between SEAPODYM predicted biomass and acoustic signal.

Example of comparison for one transect between predicted biomass in the lower mesopelagic layer and acoustic signal in epipelagic (a), upper mesopelagic (b) and lower mesopelagic (c) vertical layers and estimated values of alpha for various transects in the Pacific and Indian Ocean.

6.2. IMR acoustic observation model

Nils Olav Handegard presented the plan at IMR for implementing a simulation framework for pelagic fish observation system simulator. This work will include an observation model to translate the NORWECOM.EZE model states to acoustic backscatter and use that to simulate an observing system simulation for the important pelagic fisheries in the Norwegian Sea and adjacent waters (Figure 14). NORWECOM.EZE¹ combines several modules to simulate nutrient cycling and the lower trophic levels, ie primary production and zooplankton and different Individual Based Models of zooplankton (*Calanus finmarchicus*, *Calanus hyperboreus*), krill (*Meganyctiphanes norvegica*) and fish (mackerel, herring, blue whiting). There are ongoing developments to include mesopelagic fish.

The objective is to adopt the MESOPP observation model approach and fit it to the Norwegian case, demonstrating that it can be used as a general framework. The framework is being develop in the IMR project PELFOSS funded by the Norwegian fisheries industry (Fiskeri- og havbruksnæringens Forskningsfond) with the objective to simulate various sampling systems. A sub objective is to investigate how data collected from the fishing fleet can augment current monitoring programs. This is aligned with the MESOPP objectives, and the framework can be used to investigate how different sampling systems can be deployed to parameterize the ecosystem models in MESOPP and align it with the OSSE in SEAPODYM model framework.

¹ <http://www.imr.no/temasider/modeller/norwecom.e2e/en>

The Norwecom model predicts distributions and an observation model is being built to estimate the corresponding backscatter. The predicted backscatter will be compared to real observations, following the concept outlined in Handegard et al. (2013).

Figure 14 - Distribution of commercially important species in the north Atlantic (from Trenkel et al 2014).

6.3. CSIRO's progress in acoustic observation modeling

Rudy Kloser presented the methods to measure gas-bladder size distribution when using a probing platform. This highlighted the challenges faced in attribution of acoustic scattering to both organism type (fish, siphonophore) and the size of organism weight and length based on the gas bladder (Kloser et al 2016 and Davison et al 2015). In developing an observation model framework the sensitivity of the conversion of the ecological model to acoustic observation needs to be explored to evaluate what the acoustic signals are actually measuring and how sensitive they are to the various taxa/functional/energetic groups. To do this a forward and inverse modelling approach will be explored for various sites in the Tasman Sea, Southern Ocean and the Great Australian Bight. Available acoustic and ecological models will be used to explore the conversion of size based functional groups into acoustic scattering to compare with the acoustic and optical data as outlined in Handegard et al. (2013).

Multi-frequency/broadband acoustic and optical probe data will be used in conjunction with multi-frequency/broadband vessel and net retain catches to explore the acoustic scattering of organisms and their distribution by depth (Figure 15).

Figure 15 - The Profiling Lagrangian Acoustic Optical Sampler (PLAOS)

Image of the PLAOS being deployed to 1000 m. Vessel's 38 kHz and 18 kHz echograms with the PLAOS profile overlaid and number of single targets of strength in dB recorded per 100 m depth bin at 38 kHz and 120 kHz (Kloser et al 2016)

6.4. Approach based on biological provinces and Individual-based modeling

Roland Proud presented an overview of what his postdoc may be doing associated with Andy Brierley and Martin Cox. Two aspects of the project would centre around firstly: the biogeography of the mesopelagic community based on environmental drivers of Deep Scattering Layer (DSL) depth and echo intensity (Proud et al., 2017), secondly, the development of an individual based model of mesopelagic fish behaviour to explore scattering layer spatial (vertical arrangement in the water-column) and temporal (DVM) dynamics.

Roland's PhD thesis was devoted to the analysis of Deep Scattering Layers as observed from acoustic transects. This work has revealed pronounced differences in DSL depth and biomass across frontal zones and suggested the possibility of a global Deep Scattering Layer biogeography (Figure 16). He will embark on the Antarctic Circumpolar Expedition (ACE) to collect more acoustic data in the SO to confirm these important results.

Figure 16 - Southern Ocean mesopelagic biogeography (adapted from Proud et al., in press).

Mesopelagic classes (C1-C10) have characteristic Deep Scattering Layer depth and density (echo intensity) values. Intended Antarctic Circumpolar Expedition cruise track overlaid.

One additional key objective of Roland’s postdoc is to contribute to the development of the acoustic observation model by developing an individual-based model of vertically migrating organisms and their acoustic response under different conditions. This work will be conducted in collaboration with Nils Olav Handegard and Rudy Kloser, in order to deliver objectives outlined in the observation model section:

Figure 17 - Observation model work-flow for a given acoustic frequency

Green boxes represent observations/model output, red boxes are models to be developed and blue boxes are products. In some cases, data will not be available (dashed lines).

Observations (physical properties of the water-column and net/trawl data) made in, and model output for, each of the three regions will feed into the observation model (Figure 17). The IBM will consider time of day, environment and behaviour to determine the swimbladder volume of fish. Using scattering models (e.g. distorted-wave Born approximation model) and consideration of resonant scattering (a function of acoustic frequency, depth and swimbladder volume), acoustic signal of the biological community can be predicted and compared with acoustic observations. This task will be carried out as follows:

1.) Gather Information:

Knowledge of biological groups in the Southern Ocean (anatomy/DVM behaviour)

Obtain relevant scattering models from literature and highlight gaps in our understanding/knowledge.

2.) Model Development:

Classification of biology into acoustic scattering groups.

Assignment of scattering models to acoustic scattering groups.

Development of the Individual-based model to predict Swimbladder volume for a given state (day/night, environment).

Predict acoustic signal for 1 out of 3 regions and compare to acoustic observations.

Adjust model parameters to minimise error and perform a sensitivity analysis.

3.) Model Validation

Predict acoustic signal for the other 2 regions and compare with observations.

The development of the IBM will not only provide information regarding swimbladder state, but will also provide a platform to assess emergent system wide properties, concerning scattering formation and dynamics, which are intricately linked to the behaviour of deep-diving predators.

6.5. General Discussion on Observation Models

There are two approaches to develop an observation model, either starting from the observed signal and model it to convert the observation into a standard unit used by various models, or conversely starting from the model reference unit to predict the observed signal. This (reverse) solution is generally preferred by modelers as they prefer to keep the raw observation and can modify and improve their observation model easily. However, in that case it means that there would be one observation model for each ecosystem/micronekton model. All of them however, should use a large common basis, especially concerning the acoustic signal treatment.

Another key point is the approach to deal with missing scatterers in the ecosystem models that is contributing to acoustic backscatter, and conversely to unobserved organisms (e.g. in the first ten meters at the surface). An observation matrix needs to be established for each model to link what is observed and what is modelled. This should help as well for model intercomparison.

The use of multiple-frequencies/broad band should then advance our knowledge of scattering types and their limitations. It will be essential to further develop in parallel the models with the new observation systems. Optical and acoustic sensor packages may be useful to explore to fill the gaps in knowledge about the response of various organisms to different acoustic frequencies.

6.6. ACTIONS AND DELIVERABLES:

- List of deliverable

N°	Title	Due date	Resp.
D4.2	Methods to downscale model states to replicate acoustic signals in model validation	30/11/2017	AAD
D3.7	Observation model for micronekton	30/11/2017	IMR

- List of actions

Issue	Proposition
List existing approaches	Develop a common documentation on sharepoint

7. Conclusion of the workshop

The deliverables have been rapidly listed. The project will provide 3 references datasets of existing 38 kHz acoustic data in three different regions of the Southern Ocean (South Indian; South Pacific and South Atlantic). New data with 2, 3 or more frequencies should be collected during the project to provide information on the range of uncertainty when using only one frequency and also to give insights for the future needs (roadmap).

The Central information System (CIS) will be a key milestone to deliver project outputs (data and model outputs) to partners and external users. It will require definition of data policy, standard format and the catalogue of products.

The use cases will produce several deliverables including an Atlas of the main mesopelagic fishes, and several reports, some of them being also converted into scientific papers.

Four young researchers postdoc contracts are proposed with the project. Two of them are already starting and present to the workshop (A. Conchon and R. Proud). CSIRO has obtained a PhD grant that is proposed with a subject linked to MESOPP deliverables.

The 2nd workshop, devoted to users, is proposed to be organized by the University of Saint Andrews back to back with the first international symposium on Krill, 12-18 June 2017 (<http://synergy.st-andrews.ac.uk/3iks/>). Tentative dates of in 7-9 June 2017 are proposed for the workshop. The conference and the presence of the Sea Mammal Research Unit (<http://www.smru.st-andrews.ac.uk/>) should help to attract a lot of potential users on acoustic and micronekton data to the workshop. The third workshop, devoted to innovation, is proposed to be held in Davos, Switzerland after the SCAR-OSC conference in June 2018 (<http://www.polar2018.org>).

8. References

- Blanchard JL, Jennings S, Law R, Castle MD, McCloghrie P, et al. (2009). How does abundance scale with body size in coupled size-structured food webs? *Journal of Animal Ecology*, 78, (1) pp. 270-280. ISSN 0021-8790
- Blanchard JL, Law R, Castle MD, Jennings S (2011). Coupled energy pathways and the resilience of size-structured food webs', *Theoretical Ecology*, 4, (3) pp. 289-300. ISSN 1874-1738
- Blanchard JL, Jennings S, Holmes R, Harle J, Merino G, et al. (2012). Potential consequences of climate change for primary production and fish production in large marine ecosystems. Royal Society of London. *Philosophical Transactions. Biological Sciences*, 367 pp. 2979-2989. ISSN 0962-8436
- Davison, P., et al. (2015). "Acoustic biomass estimation of mesopelagic fishes: backscattering from individual populations and communities." *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 72(5): 1413-1424.
- Eyring, V., Bony, S., Meehl, G. A., Senior, C. A., Stevens, B., Stouffer, R. J., and Taylor, K. E.: Overview of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) experimental design and organization, *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 9, 1937-1958, doi:10.5194/gmd-9-1937-2016, 2016.
- Handegard, N. O., et al. (2013). "Towards an acoustic-based coupled observation and modelling system for monitoring and predicting ecosystem dynamics of the open ocean." *Fish and Fisheries* 14(4): 605-615.
- Handegard, Nils Olav, Louis du Buisson, Patrice Brehmer, Stewart J Chalmers, Alex De Robertis, Geir Huse, Rudy Kloser, et al. "Towards an Acoustic-Based Coupled Observation and Modelling System for Monitoring and Predicting Ecosystem Dynamics of the Open Ocean." *Fish and Fisheries* 14, no. 4 (2013): 605-615. doi:10.1111/j.1467-2979.2012.00480.x
- ICES (2013). A metadata convention for processed acoustic data from active acoustic systems, SISP 3 TG-AcMeta. ICES WGFASST Topic Group, TG-AcMeta: 35 pp.
- Kloser, R. J., et al. (2016). "Deep-scattering layer, estimates of gas-bladder size and density using a two frequency acoustic and optical probe." *ICES Journal of Marine Science* doi:10.1093/icesjms/fsv257: 12 pp.
- Kloser R.J., Williams A., Van Ruth P.D., Tanner J.E., Downie R., Doubell M., Flynn A. et al. (2016). RV Investigator voyage summary IN2015_CO2: Great Australian Bight deep-water pelagic and benthic ecosystem study. 30th Nov. to 22nd Dec. http://www.mnf.csiro.au/-/media/Files/Voyage-plans-and-summaries/Investigator/Voyage%20Plans%20summaries/2015/IN2015_CO2%20Voyage%20Summary-20160220-FINAL-optimised.ashx
- Kloser, R. J., et al. (2009). "Acoustic observations of micronekton fish on the scale of an ocean basin: potential and challenges." *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 66: 998-1006.
- Lehodey P., André J-M., Bertignac M., Hampton J., Stoens A., C. Menkès, L., Memery, Grima N., (1998). Predicting skipjack tuna forage distributions in the Equatorial Pacific using a coupled dynamical bio-geochemical model. *Fisheries Oceanography*, 7: 317-325
- Lehodey P., Murtugudde R., Senina I. (2010). Bridging the gap from ocean models to population dynamics of large marine predators: a model of mid-trophic functional groups. *Progress in Oceanography*, 84: 69-84
- Lehodey, P., Conchon, A., Senina, I., Domokos, R., Calmettes, B., Jouanno, J., Hernandez, O., and Kloser, R. (2015) Optimization of a micronekton model with acoustic data. - *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 72(5): 1399-1412, doi:10.1093/icesjms/fsu233
- Proud, R., et al. (2015). "A method for identifying Sound Scattering Layers and extracting key characteristics." *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* doi: 10.1111/2041-210X.12396: 9 pp.
- Proud, R., Cox, M.J., and Brierley, A.S. (in press). Biogeography of the Global Ocean's Mesopelagic Zone. *Current Biology*.

Ryan, T. E., et al. (2009). "Measurement and visual verification of fish target strength using an acoustic-optical system attached to a trawl net." *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 66: 1238-1244.

Ryan, T., et al. (2015). "Reducing bias due to noise and attenuation in open-ocean echo integration data." *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 72(8): 2482-2493.

Scott F, Blanchard JL, Andersen KH, (2014). mizer: an R package for multispecies, trait-based and community size spectrum ecological modeling. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 5, (10) pp. 1151-1125

ASAM (2016). Report of the meeting of the subgroup on Acoustic Survey and Analysis Methods, Commission for the Conservation of Antarctic Marine Living Resources. SG-ASAM-16: 19 pp.

Trenkel, V., Berger, L., Bourguignon, S., Doray, M., Fablet, R., Massé, J., Mazauric, V., Poncelet, C., Quemener, G., Scalabrin, C., et al. (2009). Overview of recent progress in fisheries acoustics made by Ifremer with examples from the Bay of Biscay. *Aquatic Living Resources* 22, 433-445

Trenkel, V. M., G. Huse, B. R. MacKenzie, P. Alvarez, H. Arrizabalaga, M. Castonguay, N. Goñi, et al. "Comparative Ecology of Widely Distributed Pelagic Fish Species in the North Atlantic: Implications for Modelling Climate and Fisheries Impacts." *Progress in Oceanography*, North Atlantic Ecosystems, the role of climate and anthropogenic forcing on their structure and function, 129, Part B (December 2014): 219-43. doi:10.1016/j.pocean.2014.04.030.

Appendix A - List of acronyms

TBC	To be confirmed
TBD	To be defined
AD	Applicable Document
RD	Reference Document
SCAR	Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR) is an inter-disciplinary committee of the International Council for Science (ICSU). SCAR is charged with initiating, developing and coordinating high quality international scientific research in the Antarctic region (including the Southern Ocean), and on the role of the Antarctic region in the Earth system.
CCAMLR	The Commission for the Conservation of Antarctic Marine Living Resources (CCAMLR) was established by international convention in 1982 with the objective of conserving Antarctic marine life. This was in response to increasing commercial interest in Antarctic krill resources, a keystone component of the Antarctic ecosystem and a history of over-exploitation of several other marine resources in the Southern Ocean.
DVM	Diel Vertical Migration or diurnal vertical migration: a typical pattern of daily vertical movement used by many meso- and bathy- pelagic organisms
IWC	The International Whaling Commission is an Inter-governmental Organisation whose purpose is the conservation of whales and the management of whaling. The legal framework of the IWC is the International Convention for the Regulation of Whaling. This Convention was established in 1946.
GOOS	GOOS is a permanent global system for observations, modelling and analysis of marine and ocean variables to support operational ocean services worldwide. GOOS provides accurate descriptions of the present state of the oceans, including living resources; continuous forecasts of the future conditions of the sea for as far ahead as possible, and the basis for forecasts of climate change.
IMBER	Previously known as OCEANS, IMBER was initiated by the IGBP/SCOR Ocean Futures Planning Committee in 2001. The intention was to identify the effects of global change on the ocean and the most important biological and chemical aspects of the ocean's role in global change.
ICED	Integrating Climate and Ecosystem Dynamics in the Southern Ocean http://www.iced.ac.uk/index.htm . ICED is an international multidisciplinary programme launched in response to the increasing need to develop integrated circumpolar analyses of Southern Ocean climate and ecosystem dynamics. It has been developed in conjunction with SCAR, the Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research (SCOR) and the International Geosphere-Biosphere Programme (IGBP), through joint support from the Integrated Marine Biogeochemistry and Ecosystem Research (IMBER) and Global Ocean Ecosystem Dynamics (GLOBEC) programmes. The ICED vision is to develop a coordinated circumpolar approach to better understand climate interactions in the Southern Ocean, the implications for ecosystem dynamics, the impacts on biogeochemical cycles, and the development of sustainable management procedures.

9. Attachment A

Mesopelagic Southern Ocean Prey and Predators

Workshop: "Towards standards of acoustic data for micronekton modeling"

CSIRO, Hobart, Tasmania 10-13 Sep. 2016

List of participants

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10. Status of deliverables

Deliverables

For each Deliverable, a single file (max 52MB) can be uploaded

WP No	Del Rel	D	Title	Lead Benefi	Nature	Dissemination t	Est. Del. Dat ▲	Receipt Date
WP1	D1.1	D	Project Management plan	CLS	Report	Confidential,	31 Jul 2016	29 Jul 2016
WP1	D1.2	D	Quarterly project progress report including technical and finance period report	CLS	Report	Confidential,	31 Aug 2016	01 Sep 2016
WP1	D1.4	D	Dissemination & exploitation plan	CLS	Report	Public	31 Aug 2016	30 Aug 2016
WP1	D1.5	D	Dissemination through web site and social networks	CLS	Websites, patent	Public	31 Aug 2016	30 Aug 2016
WP2	D2.4	D	First release of web site	CLS	Websites, patent	Public	31 Aug 2016	30 Aug 2016
WP2	D2.1	D	Report on Workshop 1	CSIRO	Other	Public	31 May 2017	
WP4	D4.1	D	Report and manuscript of outcomes of Tasks 4.1.1 and 4.1.2 (documentation of the models, approaches for standardisation and protocols to be used for model inter-comparisons)	UTAS	Report	Public	31 May 2017	
WP2	D2.5	D	Release of web site with e-infrastructure (catalogue and data access services	CLS	ORDP: Open Rese	Public	30 Nov 2017	
WP3	D3.2	D	Reference dataset of 38 kHz acoustic backscatter for South Atlantic sector Southern Ocean	NERC-BAS	Other	Public	30 Nov 2017	
WP3	D3.3	D	Reference dataset of 38 kHz acoustic backscatter for South Indian ocean sector	UPMC	Other	Public	30 Nov 2017	
WP3	D3.4	D	Reference dataset of 38 kHz acoustic backscatter for South Pacific Ocean sector	CSIRO	Other	Public	30 Nov 2017	
WP3	D3.5	D	Collocated NASC and oceanographic variables	UPMC	Other	Public	30 Nov 2017	
WP3	D3.6	D	report on observation and ecological model links using current methods and estimates of taxonomic/ functional/ energetic group resolution and precision	CSIRO	Report	Public	30 Nov 2017	
WP4	D4.2	D	Scientific manuscript of methods to downscale model states to replicate acoustic signals in model validation	AAD	Report	Public	30 Nov 2017	
WP4	D4.6	D	Atlas of the main mesopelagic fish based on international database	UPMC	Report	Public	30 Nov 2017	
WP2	D2.2	D	Report on Workshop 2	IMR	Other	Public	31 May 2018	
WP3	D3.1	D	Report of acoustic processing routine and quality checking methods	NERC-BAS	Report	Public	31 May 2018	
WP4	D4.3	D	Scientific manuscript of methods to rapidly aggregate acoustic data from vessels of opportunity for use in model validation	UTAS	Report	Public	31 May 2018	
WP4	D4.7	D	Modelisation of potential habitats of the main mesopelagic fish according to environmental parameters	USTAN	Report	Public	31 May 2018	
WP4	D4.8	D	Joint analysis of existing acoustic measures with micronekton models, in situ measurements of plankton and fish to identify 3D segregation of species assemblages and biomass.	UPMC	Report	Public	31 May 2018	
WP2	D2.7	D	Roadmap towards a global integrated observing and modelling system.	IMR	Report	Public	30 Nov 2018	
WP3	D3.7	D	Report on observation model links for micronekton comparing existing and new acoustic technology and state of the art model-observation links	IMR	Report	Public	30 Nov 2018	
WP4	D4.4	D	Publication on statistical methods for estimating skill of mesopelagic models to replicate acoustic observations	CLS	Report	Public	30 Nov 2018	
WP4	D4.9	D	Use of micronekton data and models to improve ecology of top predators	USTAN	Report	Public	30 Nov 2018	
WP2	D2.6	D	Final release with update of products	CLS	Websites, patent	Public	31 Mar 2019	
WP1	D1.3	D	Final report	CLS	Report	Public	31 May 2019	
WP1	D1.6	D	Dissemination Report	CLS	Report	Public	31 May 2019	
WP2	D2.3	D	Report on Workshop 3	UTAS	Other	Public	31 May 2019	
WP4	D4.5	D	Report and publication on model inter-comparison, including publication of the methods used in this projec	UTAS	Report	Public	31 May 2019	
WP4	D4.10	D	Joint Australian and French reports to CCAMLR	AAD	Report	Public	31 May 2019	

